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THE STUDY OF GENDER DIFFERENCES AND RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MARITAL ADJUSTMENT AND SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING AMONG SINGLE AND DUAL EARNER COUPLES IN INDIAN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to examine the gender differences in marital adjustment and subjective well-being among single and dual earner couples between 25 to 45 years of age range (working couples= 100; male =50 and female=50, Single earner couples= 100; working male=50, non-working female=50) . The total sample consisted of 200 participants. Marital Adjustment Questionnaire (MAQ) developed by KanchanaRohatgi and Pramod Kumar and The Satisfaction with Life Scale developed by Ed. Diener were used for collection of data. . Exploratory analyses and two way ANOVA was applied across gender and variables. Correlation analysis was carried out in order to have a better understanding about the relationship among variable. The results indicate that there is no significant gender difference in marital adjustment among single and dual earner couples ($P>.05$). It also reveals that there is significant gender difference in subjective well-being among single and dual earner couples ($P<.05$). It also indicates that there is significant positive correlation between marital adjustment and subjective well-being.

Keywords:

Gender differences, Marital Adjustment and Subjective well-being.

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is defined as a union between a man and a woman in all the spheres of life. In India, marriage is also named as “ Vivah” and “ Nikah “. "Marital adjustment" refers to overall level to which the individuals have fitted together into a smooth, functioning dyad. ". In keeping with Burgess and Cottrell (1939), " a well - adjusted marriage is also a wedding during which the attitude and actions of each of the partners produce an environment which is very favorable to proper functioning of the personality structures of every partner." Vincent (1981) feels that the goal of marital adjustment is self - fulfillment for both partners together without sacrificing the individual self - fulfillment of either. In another study Sinha & Mukerjee (1990) defines marital adjustment as "the state during which there's an overall feeling in husband and wife of happiness and satisfaction with their marriage and with each other .". Therefore, the basis to establish adjustment in marriage is mutual communication and sharing. Marital adjustment therefore, involves maturity that accepts and understands growth and development within the spouse. The basis for marital adjustment is the reward obtained from spousal interaction

Subjective well-being designed to capture information about how people experience their lives. They're supported individual's self-reports, an common measures include questions about whether people feel satisfied , content and fulfilled in their lives overall, furthermore as a variety of more day-to-day emotions, like happiness , worry , depression and sadness. The term subjective well-being emphasizes an individual's own assessment of his or her own life. In step with Ed Diener, an American psychologist, subjective well-being is multidimensional and includes positive and negative emotions (e.g. the frequency, duration and intensity of joy, pleasure, happiness

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but also anger, guilt, fear, depression, sadness), also as global life satisfaction, and satisfaction with different aspects of one's life (partnership, income, friends) . The determinants and consequences of happiness needs to be measured separately.

• **Life evaluation** – which refers to reflective assessments of a person's life as a complete, or some specific aspect of life.

• **Affect** – which refers to both positive and negative feelings and emotions, like happiness, contentment, worry, sadness, depression, anger, fear, etc.

• **Eudaimonia** – a various and (as yet) less well-defined construct, often accustomed confer with feelings of meaning and purpose in life (capturing the thought of a life “lived well”).

Association between Marital Adjustment and Subjective well-being

Antoaneta Andria Moraru in Romania in 2013, reported that there are almost no differences between men and women in marital adjustment. In a very research Dr. ShikhaGoel, Dr. Darshan Kaur Narang, Dr. KavitaKoradia concluded that Couples are having better marital adjustment during early adulthood than in late adulthood. Even if, working females play dual roles and are over burdened but still they fight to create adjustments in family and are satisfied and funky under all circumstances. In a study conducted on Effect of gender differences in subjective well-being among dual-earner couples by Sameshta, and Dr. Sunita Agarwal in India in 2017. Result indicates that husbands experience more life satisfaction and frequent joy as compared to their wives. Compared to men, women are expected to figure more as homemakers and caregivers.

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this study was to examine the gender differences and relationship between Marital adjustment and Subjective well-being among single and dual earner couples

METHODOLOGY

. The Null Hypothesis was formulated, which states:

1. There will be no difference in the degree of marital adjustment among dual and single earner couples
2. There will be no difference in the degree of subjective well-being among dual and single earner couples
3. There will be no correlation between marital adjustment and subjective well-being among Single and Dual earner couples

A total of 200 participants (Dual earner couples =100; males= 50 ; females =50 and Single earning Couples =100; working males =50; non- working females =50) were included in the study ,within 25 to 45 years of age range .

MEASURES

• Marital Adjustment Questionnaire (MAQ)

Marital Adjustment Questionnaire by Pramod Kumar and KanchanaRohatgi (1999) is used. This scale is a simple measure of marital adjustment. The measure are often used as a quick screen to spot degree of marital adjustment. The scale involves 25 questions with dichotomous options (Yes / No). A 'yes' response is assigned a score1 apart from items 4, 10 and 19 during which case reverse is applicable. This tool is meant for married couples with age running from 28-60 years.

• Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS)

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS), a self-reported measure of well-being developed by Ed Diener in 1984, is based on a tripartite model of subjective well-being . The scale includes five items which assess the general level of the individual's satisfaction with life. Respondents answer in a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly

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agree). Items are added up so as to yield a complete score of life satisfaction. The possible range of scores is between 5 and 35, with greater scores signifying higher satisfaction with life.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained in the research were analyzed by using appropriate statistical techniques in SPSS. Descriptive statistical analysis of the data was made. The analysis was done by Mean, Standard Deviation, Two way ANOVA and Correlation among variables. The significance coefficient was taken as .05. There were 200 participants in the study.

Table 3.1.1 Showing Mean & S.D of Single & Dual Earner Couples in Marital Adjustment (N=200)

Scales	Group of Gender	Mean	S.D
Marital Adjustment	DEMC	16.90	2.85
	DEFC	17.48	3.34
	SEMC	16.66	2.43
	SEFC	16.68	2.93
	N	200	

Fig.3.1.2 Bar Chart representing Mean & S.D of Single & Dual earner couples in Marital Adjustment

The Figure 3.1.2. showing Mean & S.D. value of Dual earner couples & Single earner couples on Marital Adjustment . It indicates that the mean score of (17.48) the dual earner female couple is comparatively larger than the mean score of (16.90) the dual earner male couple in Marital Adjustment . It also indicates that the mean score of (16.68) the single earner female couple is comparatively larger than the mean score of (16.66) the single earner male couple in Marital Adjustment . Though there is least difference among them on the measure.. It also indicates that the

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mean score of dual earner female couple is comparatively larger than other three groups in Marital Adjustment.

Table 3.1.3 Showing Mean & S.D of Single & Dual Earner Couples on Satisfaction With Life. (N=200)

Scales	Group of Gender	Mean	S.D
Satisfaction with Life Scale	DEMC	46.52	3.25
	DEFC	46.88	2.51
	SEMC	43.30	3.05
	SEFC	43.22	4.38
	N	200	

Fig. 3.1.4 Bar Chart representing Mean & S.D of Single & Dual Earner Couples in Satisfaction With Life Scale.

The Figure 3.1.4. showing Mean & S.D. value of Dual earner couples & Single earner couples on Satisfaction With Life Scale . It indicates that the mean score of (46.88) the dual earner female couple is comparatively larger than the mean score of (46.52) the dual earner male couple in Satisfaction with Life Scale .Although there is least difference among them on the measure. It also indicates that the mean score of (43.30) the single earner male couple is comparatively larger than the mean score of (43.22) the single earner female couple in Satisfaction with Life Scale . Though there is least difference among them on the measure. It also indicates that the mean score of dual earner female couple is comparatively larger than the other three groups in Satisfaction with Life Scale.

Table 3.2.1 (A) Showing the Summary of the 2x2 ANOVA for Gender on Marital Adjustment (N=200)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	p-value
Gender	21.94	3	7.31	.86	.46	Not Significant

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Table 3. 2.1.(A) . depicts F value for Gender on Marital Adjustment . Significant (F= .863 ,(3,196) P> 0.05) no difference was found between male and female on marital adjustment. On this basis it can be observed that gender has an influencing factor to determine level of adjustment in marital life. Thus it can be concluded that there is marginal difference between male and female couples in marital adjustment . Although the working female exhibit more adjustment in marital life than male counterparts. In case of single earner couples , adjustment is approximately equal for both male and female.

Table 3.2.2(B) Showing the Summary of the 2x2 ANOVA for Gender on Satisfaction with Life Scale.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	p-value
Gender	595.08	3	198.36	17.44	.00	Significant

Table 3.2.2(B). depicts F value for Gender on Satisfaction with Life . Significant (F=17.443 , (3,196) P<0.05) difference was found between male and female on satisfaction with life . On this basis it can be observed that gender has an influencing factor to determine level of satisfaction with life . Thus it can be concluded that there is difference between male and female couples in satisfaction with life. The dual earner female couples exhibit more satisfaction with life than their counterparts. Although , there is less difference in their level of satisfaction with Life. In case of single earner couples satisfaction with life is approximately equal.

Table .3.3 Showing the Correlation Matrix between Marital Adjustment & Satisfaction with Life.

VARIABLES	CORRELATION
Marital Adjustment & Satisfaction with Life	.251**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3.3 represents the correlation between the research variables. It indicates significant positive correlation between marital adjustment and satisfaction with life (.251**). It shows that with better marital adjustment, satisfaction with life also improves and vice-versa.

DISCUSSION

The research was undertaken to investigate the gender differences in marital adjustment and subjective well-being among single and dual earner couples between 25 to 45 years of age range (working couples= 100; male =50 and female=50, Single earner couples= 100; working male=50, non-working female=50) . The null hypothesis was formulated that “There will be no difference in the degree of marital adjustment and subjective well-being among dual and single earner couples.” is accepted. The results indicate that there is no significant difference among Single and dual earner couples in marital adjustment.

Though there is least difference among them on the measure. It also indicates that the mean score of dual earner female couple is comparatively higher than the other three groups in Marital Adjustment. And dual earner couples have better marital adjustment than single earner couples. Although the difference in the degree of marital adjustment is least among all the groups .These findings are consistent with the results obtained from the analyses of data from National Study of Families and

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Households (Gager& Sanchez, 2003) that indicated that nearly 80% of couples had the same marital adjustment and, among the remaining couples who reported different scores, the proportion of husbands and wives who reported lower scores was virtually equal. In the present time, both the working males and working female partners try to establish balance in both the household responsibilities and their professional duties too. Unlike the traditional Indian marriage system where husbands and wives expect each other to follow gender based division of labor where the husband is responsible for financially supporting the family and the wife is responsible for household works and child rearing. The couples understand that in order to have a balanced married life they need to act as a unit where cooperation is essential and one must not feel burden to manage things alone. The male spouses in the present time are not as rigid as the earlier ones. One most important reason is that male spouse is not dominating because of several protective laws for women empowerment. On the other hand, female spouses have also gained self confidence which was strongly missing in the past female partners. This is supported by a study conducted by Antoaneta Andria Moraru in Romania in 2013. They studied if there are differences between men and women in relationship and marital adjustment. They reported that there are almost no differences between men and women in marital adjustment. The importance of education is noticeable in the present study. In contrast to the previous researches in marital adjustment where women were found to have lower marital adjustment scores, the findings from the present research indicates dual earner female couples are doing good in their marital life too along with managing their professional roles. The mutual understanding and cooperation from their copartner is undoubtedly helping them to manage her household roles and professional life too. This is because in the present scenario males are turning towards the realistic aspects of life where they are less demanding and more cooperative as compared to the earlier male attitude towards life. Also because they realize that it is worthy to live joyfully for both mental and physical health. Because prolong stress could lead to loss of one's wellbeing and also of people associated to them. The findings are interesting because most previous studies have reported that single earner couples has better marital adjustment than dual earner couples (Bhikaji& Hari ,2016) , but the findings from the present research has different results.

The results also indicate that there is significant difference among single and dual earner couples in subjective well-being. It indicates that dual earner couples are better on the measure of satisfaction with life than single earner couples. It also indicates that dual earner female couples are comparatively better on the measure of satisfaction with life than the other three groups. Although, there is less difference among them. This finding is supported by Hyde (2005) who proposed that men and women are more similar than they are different. She further added that many gender differences are extremely small on the measure of subjective well-being. The different components and constructs of well-being need to be defined.

The third null hypothesis which states that "There will be no correlation between marital adjustment and subjective well-being" has been rejected because the findings indicate significant positive correlation between marital adjustment and satisfaction with life. This finding is supported byBasharpoor S, Sheykholeslami A (2015) who reported that each one dimensions of family functions and dyadic adjustment were positively correlated with quality of life.

CONCLUSION

1. There is no significant difference in marital adjustment among single and dual earner couples. Dual earner female couple is comparatively better than the other three groups in Marital Adjustment. And dual earner couples have better marital adjustment than single earner couples. Although the difference in the degree of marital adjustment is least among all the groups.
2. There is significant difference among single and dual earner couples in subjective well-being. Dual earner couples are better on the measure of satisfaction with life than single earner couples.

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And dual earner female couples are comparatively better on the measure of satisfaction with life than the other three groups. Although, there is less difference among them.

3. There is significant positive correlation between marital adjustment and subjective well-being among single and dual earner couples.

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COMPETING INTEREST

No competing interest exist.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

The research has been conducted under the supervision of Dr. AnshubhiBahadur. The Complete procedure of designing, literature review, data collection, statistical analysis, and editing of the research paper is done by Raksha Singh, the Corresponding Author of this research article.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

All authors hereby declare that the complete study have been performed in accordance with the ethical standards of American Psychological Association.

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